

THE EFFECT OF A COMPLIANT INTERPHASE ON THE TRANSVERSE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC COMPOSITES

K.R.J.Ellis* and M.G.Phillips

School of Materials Science , University of Bath , Bath , BA2 7AY , England

(* now with European Friction Industries , Bristol , BS4 5NZ , England)

ABSTRACT

It has been postulated that the introduction of a compliant material between the glass fibre and polymer matrix could significantly reduce stress or strain magnifications in the composite. This in turn would lead to improved performance particularly transverse to the fibre axis.

The Kies model for prediction of transverse tensile strain magnification in the resin between fibres was extended to include a thin interphase. Variations in interphase properties could then be modelled to assess their effects on strain magnification in the resin. The model predicts that a low modulus , high elongation interphase would significantly reduce matrix strain magnifications leading to improved transverse tensile strength.

Composites were manufactured which contained a thin compliant interphase between fibre and matrix. However , transverse tensile tests showed no improvement in strength when using the interphase. A possible explanation for this lack of improvement was that the interphase material no longer exhibits its bulk properties of low modulus when it is very thin , due to constraint by the adjacent phases.

Dynamic mechanical analysis measurements were made to determine the modulus of the interphase material in the form of a coating on a steel substrate. The modulus was shown to increase by orders of magnitude as thickness was reduced such that it approached that of the matrix resin. The model then predicts no reduction in matrix strain magnification. It is concluded that to achieve the anticipated improvement in transverse tensile performance a low modulus material with a Poisson's ratio of 0.33 is required for the interphase.

KEYWORDS: Fibre , glass ; Interphase ; Polymer ; Transverse ; Unidirectional.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the strength of a unidirectional fibre composite is significantly lower when loaded in a direction transverse to the main fibre axis. Although composite structures are designed to minimise these transverse loads it is practically impossible to eliminate them completely. Complex loading and gripping arrangements can often lead to significant transverse stresses which might well be sufficient to cause premature failure of the composite structure. Means of improving the transverse strength of a unidirectional composite without significantly affecting the longitudinal properties were therefore sought.

It has been postulated (1-9) that by employing a third, comparatively thin, material at the interface between the fibre and the matrix, stress or strain concentrations could be reduced. This third phase is commonly known as the interphase. By suitable choice of interphase material and thickness composite properties such as strength, failure strain, toughness and fatigue life, particularly transverse to the fibre axis, might be improved.

Two general possibilities exist for the interphase material. Either it should be of intermediate modulus to reduce the modulus mismatch between adjacent phases, or it should be of low modulus to allow for large deformations at the interface. Review of the work to date indicated that for improvement of transverse properties the low modulus approach had the greatest chance of success. To aid in making the optimum choice of interphase material and thickness a simple theoretical model was developed.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL FOR TRANSVERSE TENSILE STRAIN MAGNIFICATION

2.1 Kies two-phase model Kies (10) developed a model for the prediction of transverse tensile strain magnification in the resin between fibres for a unidirectional composite. He considered two adjacent lines of load in a transverse section through an idealised square array composite (figure 1). One line (line A-B) passes through two fibres while the second (line C-D) passes through no fibres. If the composite is strained by an amount ϵ_t , then the matrix along C-D will also be strained by ϵ_t . The matrix between the fibres however, along E-F, will be strained by some larger amount ϵ_m . This is because the fibres are significantly stiffer than the matrix and so deflect less under the applied load. Since the total deflection must be constant the matrix between the fibres must deflect more to make up the difference. Kies showed that this strain magnification, defined as $\frac{\epsilon_m}{\epsilon_t}$, is given by :

$$\frac{\epsilon_m}{\epsilon_t} = \frac{2r + s}{s + 2r \left(\frac{E_m}{E_f} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where r is the fibre radius, s the interfibre spacing, E_f the fibre transverse modulus, and E_m the resin modulus.

For a typical glass fibre reinforced composite material with the following parameters:

fibre radius (r)	: 6 μm
fibre volume fraction (V)	: 0.5
fibre modulus (E_f)	: 76 GPa
resin modulus (E_m)	: 3 GPa

the tensile strain magnification factor in the resin is 4.28. As the fibre volume fraction approaches its maximum, that is when the fibres are just touching, the strain magnification factor reaches its maximum value of approximately 20. The model therefore shows how important local fibre volume fractions can be in initiating cracking in the composite structure.

2.2 Three-phase development of Kies model The original Kies model was extended to include a third interphase between the fibre and the resin matrix. This is illustrated in figure 2. New parameters were introduced to assess the effect of varying the interphase modulus and thickness.

Following Kies' original arguments a new equation for the strain magnification factor in the resin can be calculated (11). It is given by :

$$\frac{\epsilon_m}{\epsilon_i} = \frac{2r + 2t + s}{s + 2r \frac{E_m}{E_f} + 2t \frac{E_m}{E_i}} \quad (2)$$

By a similar argument the tensile strain magnification in the interphase is given by:

$$\frac{\epsilon_i}{\epsilon_r} = \frac{2r + 2t + s}{2t + 2r \frac{E_i}{E_f} + s \frac{E_i}{E_m}} \quad (3)$$

Using the previously defined parameters for the rest of the system it was found that the strain magnification factor in the resin could be reduced to 1 by assigning the following values to the interphase parameters :

interphase thickness (t) : 0.2 μ m
interphase modulus (E_i) : 0.1 GPa

This in turn resulted in a strain magnification factor in the interphase of 30. To satisfy the demands of the interphase it was obvious that a low modulus , high strain to failure material was needed. A synthetic rubber was therefore selected for assessment of the theory by experimental measurement.

3. COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE AND MECHANICAL TESTING

Composite plates were manufactured by a filament winding technique using glass fibre roving and vinyl ester resin. The synthetic rubber interphase was applied to the fibre roving by a self regulating technique which ensured a thin even coating of all the fibres. Direct observation of the thickness of the interphase was not possible and so an x-ray analysis technique was developed which could indirectly measure it. This technique is based on the work of Sewell (12) and will be described in a subsequent publication. Composite plates were manufactured with no interphase so that the effect of the interphase could be determined. Coupons of the resin and the interphase materials were also made such that their bulk mechanical properties could be determined.

Transverse tensile tests were carried out on coupons cut from composite plates both with and without the interphase. A loading rate of one millimetre per minute was used in conjunction with a non-contacting extensometer. The same technique was used for the coupons of neat resin and neat rubber.

The results of the neat resin and neat rubber tests (average of six replicates) are presented in table 1. The results of the composite plate tests (average of ten replicates) are presented in table 2. It is obvious from the results for the composite plates that no significant improvement in properties was shown when using the interphase. At this stage it was considered that a possible reason for the lack of improvement might be that the rubber interphase was not exhibiting its rubber like properties when used as a thin interphase. It was therefore decided to try to measure the change in the modulus of the rubber as it became thinner. The method used for this was dynamic mechanical analysis.

4. DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF A CONSTRAINED RUBBER COATING

Previous work by Wetton (13) has shown that the tensile modulus of a polymeric coating on a stiff substrate can be measured using dynamic mechanical analysis. Wetton was concerned with determining the elastic modulus of the coating material without having to remove it from the substrate. Wetton found that as the thickness of the coating decreased the modulus increased. This was thought to be due to constraint and Wetton determined a minimum thickness of film that could be measured before constraint significantly affected the modulus. For this project, however, it was this very effect of constraint on modulus which needed to be investigated. In a separate paper (14) Wetton presented an equation for determining the modulus of a coating on a substrate. The substrate was coated on both sides and was tested in single cantilever bending. The equation was:

$$(kE')_{composite} = E_s' b \left(\frac{t_s}{l} \right)^3 + E_c' b \left(\left(\frac{t_s + 2t_c}{l} \right)^3 - \left(\frac{t_s}{l} \right)^3 \right) \quad (4)$$

where $(kE')_{composite}$ is the measured stiffness of the "composite" (coating plus substrate) beam, E_s' and t_s are the substrate modulus and thickness, E_c' and t_c are the coating modulus and thickness, b is the beam width, and l is the mean free length of vibration of the beam.

A steel substrate 0.05 mm thick, 10 mm wide and with a free length of 9 mm was used in single cantilever bending mode. To begin with it was confirmed that the correct modulus was being measured for the steel substrate.

The next stage was to coat pieces of the shim steel with the synthetic rubber. Layers were added one at a time by dipping the steel into a solution of the rubber and then drying it off with a hot air blower. Samples were prepared which had the following number of layers of rubber; 1, 2, 4, 5, 10, 20, 35, 50. Before use, the coated beams were cured for 3 hours at 80 ° C. The coating thickness was determined by measuring the total beam thickness, subtracting the substrate thickness, and then dividing by two.

Each coated beam was measured three times, regripping to a constant torque setting each time, to determine the accuracy of each result. This was particularly important, for the free length varied slightly from the intended nine millimetres each time and had to be accurately measured. A frequency of vibration of 1 Hz was used with a peak to peak deflection of 32 micron. All measurements were made at room temperature.

The measured results were in terms of the beam stiffness. The coating modulus for each of the measurements was then calculated according to equation 4 and the results are presented in Table 3. The log values for coating thickness and modulus are plotted in figure 3. Also plotted on figure 3 is the value of modulus for the thick, unconstrained synthetic rubber, determined by dynamic mechanical analysis to be 2.88×10^7 Pa.

5. DISCUSSION

The values of modulus calculated for the interphase by this technique should not be considered as absolute. However, the results of this analysis show quite clearly that the modulus of the rubber increases significantly as the thickness decreases. The modulus value at 55 micron is already comparable with the modulus of the vinyl ester resin. It is not clear from the curve if a maximum has been reached for the modulus of the rubber or whether significant increases will occur as the thickness reduces further to the sub micron levels present in the composite.

It is unlikely that values of coating modulus could be determined at thicknesses less than those already measured. This is because the measured stiffness for the 55 micron coating thickness is very close to the stiffness value measured for the substrate only, although it is shown by Student "t" test still to be significantly different. Once these stiffness measurements become indistinguishable from one another the coating modulus can no longer be calculated.

In the context of this paper, "constraint" refers to the constraint of the Poisson's contractions that would normally occur in a material subjected to a tensile stress. The constraint occurs at the surface of a compliant material when it is bonded to a stiffer material. If the compliant material is relatively thick then these surface constraints do not significantly affect its overall response. However, if the material is thin then the whole material is constrained, leading to a triaxial stress state rather than a simple uniaxial stress state. Under these circumstances the relevant modulus of the material changes from the Young's modulus, E , to the bulk modulus, K . These moduli are related by the equation:

$$K = \frac{E}{3(1 - 2\nu)} \quad (5)$$

For any material with a Poisson's ratio above 0.333 the bulk modulus will be higher than the Young's modulus. In fact, as the Poisson's ratio approaches 0.5 the value of the bulk modulus approaches infinity. Thus, for the "rubbery" interphase material one might expect significant increases in the apparent modulus because for rubbers the Poisson's ratio is generally considered to be 0.5, or just less than 0.5. The values of constrained, or bulk modulus ($K = 1.27 \times 10^9$ Pa, table 3), and unconstrained, or Young's modulus ($E = 4.0 \times 10^7$ Pa, table 1), can be used in equation 5 to predict the Poisson's ratio for the interphase material used here. The calculated value is 0.495.

Possible effects of constraint on the matrix resin itself need to be considered. It follows from equation 5 that for materials with a Poisson's ratio of less than 0.333, such as the vinyl ester resin ($\nu = 0.3$), the bulk modulus will be slightly less than the Young's modulus. Therefore, as the resin becomes thin and constrained, that is as its Young's modulus tends towards its bulk modulus, the apparent value of the modulus will not change significantly. Thus, to use the unconstrained value of Young's modulus for the matrix resin in the model, where the resin is actually thin and constrained, should not have led to any significant errors.

6. CONCLUSIONS

To avoid an increase in interphase modulus due to Poisson's contractions a material with Poisson's ratio of 0.33 is required. A material with such a Poisson's ratio should retain its desirable properties of low modulus and high strain to failure when used as an interphase. The result would be to improve the transverse tensile strength of the composite by reducing the strain magnification factor in the resin.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described in this paper was financed by a research contract awarded to M.G. Phillips by G.K.N. Technology, Wolverhampton, U.K.

8. REFERENCES

1. JL Kardos, Chemtech, 14, 7, pp. 430-434, (1984).
2. MT Aronhime, G Marom, Unpublished research report submitted to Pioneering Research Laboratory, Du Pont, Wilmington, Delaware, (1987).
3. JL Kardos, 36th Annual Technical Conference, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, The Society of the Plastics Industry, Section 2E.
4. RE Lavengood, MJ Michno Jr., Proc. Div. Tech. Conf., Engrg. Props. And Structure Div., Society Plastics Engineers, p. 127, (1975).
5. JF Gerard, Polymer Engineering and Science, 28, 9, pp. 568-577, (1988).
6. JP Bell, J Chang, HW Rhee, R Joseph, Polymer Composites, 8, 1, pp.46-52, (1987).

7. H Ishida , Polymer Composites , 5 , 2 , pp. 101-123 , (1984).
8. RGC Arridge , Polymer Engineering and Science , 15 , 10 , pp. 757-760 , (1975).
9. G Marom , RGC Arridge , Materials Science and Engineering , 23 , pp. 23-32 , (1976).
10. JA Kies , U.S. Naval Research Laboratory Report NRL 5752 , (1962).
11. KRJ Ellis , Ph.D. Thesis , University of Bath , England , (1990).
12. DA Sewell , ID Hall , G Love , JP Partridge , VD Scott , Journal de Physique , 45 , pp. 33-36 , (1984).
13. RE Wetton , MR Stone , GE Pratt , NATAS Conference , San Fransico , Paper 2 , (1986).
14. RE Wetton , In : Developments in polymer characterisation , Applied Science Publishers , (1986).

Table 1. Properties of matrix and interphase materials in bulk. Figures in brackets are standard deviations.

Property	Matrix resin	Interphase material
Strength (MPa)	63.4 (17.3)	4.34 (1.04)
Failure strain (%)	2.4 (1.34)	1600 (150)
Young's modulus (GPa)	3.75 (0.18)	0.04 (0.02)

Table 2. Transverse tensile properties of unidirectional composites with coated and uncoated fibres. Figures in brackets are standard deviations.

Specimen	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Failure strain (%)	Fibre volume fraction (%)
Coated fibre	17.22 (2.21)	25.57 (5.71)	0.174 (0.045)	59.5 (1.0)
Uncoated fibre	17.31 (2.58)	26.81 (3.20)	0.171 (0.035)	59.5 (1.0)

Table 3. Apparent Young's modulus of interphase material in the form of a coating on a steel substrate. Effect of coating thickness. Figures in brackets are standard deviations.

Coating thickness, t (μm)	Coating modulus (MPa)	Log coating thickness	Log coating modulus
55 (5)	1267 (674)	1.74	3.103
95 (5)	1067 (262)	1.98	3.028
135 (5)	440.7 (91.9)	2.13	2.644
185 (5)	225.5 (71.4)	2.27	2.353
365 (5)	81.5 (8.9)	2.56	1.911
595 (5)	80.4 (10.6)	2.77	1.905
1200 (5)	40.8 (3.2)	3.08	1.611
1550 (5)	41.6 (1.8)	3.19	1.619

Figure 1. Parameters of the Kies model for matrix strain magnification in a fibre composite under transverse load.

Figure 2. Parameters of the modified Kies model, incorporating an interphase.

Figure 3. Young's modulus of the interphase material, in the form of a coating on a steel substrate. Points show the effect of coating thickness. Broken line indicates value for material in bulk. E is in MPa, t in micrometres.

